

ADVANTAGES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICS IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS ON THE BASIS OF PROJECT WORK

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Abstract. *Today, in-depth teaching of natural sciences to young students remains the most important and urgent issue. Modern technologies of the educational system for the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities of young students, to abandon traditional educational methods in the educational system and to replace them with non-traditional educational methods, to develop deep knowledge and constant observation are desirable to organize on the basis of this and thereby increase the attention to the development of independent thinking and creative abilities of young people. This article reflects the advantages and methods of education based on project work aimed at developing the creative abilities of young students.*

Keywords: *project work, learning by doing and living, practical experience, perception, time management, creative thinking, forecasting, teamwork, spiral curriculum, method.*

INTRODUCTION

After gaining independence, our republic chose the path of its future development based on the market economy. Competition is the basis of the market economy. This requires fundamental changes in all areas of our life. In this case, the products produced and the services provided must be in line with world standards and be competitive. This, in turn, requires our personnel, especially our youth, to be deeply and comprehensively knowledgeable. Therefore, a decree was issued to fundamentally change the education system in our republic and it is being implemented. In the development of our country, the establishment of an excellent education system based on the rich spiritual potential of the people and universal human values, as well as modern culture, economy, and the latest achievements of science, technique, and technology, is very important.

If we look at history, we will see that physics has been the fundamental basis for the creation of almost all discoveries and technologies in the world. In fact, without a deep understanding of the laws of physics, it is impossible to achieve results in today's demanding fields such as mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, "IT", water and energy saving technologies.[1]

The modern concept of natural sciences forms a real scientific worldview in students, in the explanation of animate and inanimate nature, considerations are made from the micro-macroworld to the mega-world on the basis of fundamental laws. At the same time, it shows the actual issues of the next years and natural-scientific paradigms about the single material world. If the changes in modern physics that are taking place in nature illuminate deeper and simpler maximally necessary mathematical expressions, on the other hand, it shows that the main directions of fundamental sciences are developing in the current period.

Learning by doing is a theory that emphasizes student engagement and is a hands-on, task-oriented, learning process.[2] Theory refers to the process of active participation of students in more practical and imaginative ways of learning. This process differs from other educational approaches because it offers many pedagogical advantages over more traditional teaching methods, such as the emphasis on tacit knowledge.[3] Learning by doing is related to other types of learning, such as adventure learning, action learning, cooperative learning, experiential learning, peer learning, service-based learning, and experiential learning.

Learning by Living is an online school that uses real-life knowledge and real-life learning as its curriculum.

THE FOUNDERS

Much of what is known about learning-by-doing theory was due to the contributions of historical minds that have transformed education today. This theory was revealed and popularized by the famous American philosopher and crusader John Dewey and the Brazilian educator Paulo Freire. Dewey, who is considered one of the founders of modern functional psychology, implemented this idea by establishing a laboratory school at the University of Chicago. His views are important in establishing advanced educational practices. He was a supporter of progressive education as opposed to traditional education. Dewey believed that effective learning takes place through interactions, and that the school is a social institution where these interactions occur. In an ideal learning-by-doing classroom, the classroom is a space for children to learn and solve problems in their own way, at their own pace, with the guidance of a child-sensitive teacher. It develops a healthy and responsive learning community where students actively participate in the learning process. Learning by doing focuses not only on academic growth, but also on social, intellectual, emotional, physical and spiritual growth.

On the other hand, Freire, based on his most influential work known as Pedagogy of the Oppressed, emphasized the important role of individual development, seeking to build awareness and develop critical skills. Dewey advocated education as a means of maintaining democracy and healthy government because he grew up in progressive and cultured New York City. While in Brazil during the dictatorship, Freire lived a life of poverty and misery. Therefore, he advocated education as a means of awareness and relief from the problems of underdevelopment. Thus, these experiences will be a contributing factor in how he constructs his ideas about education.

In addition to Freire and Dewey, there were other major contributors to learning theory, including Richard Du Four, who used and applied it to the development of professional learning communities. Richard Du Four was an educational consultant and author who wanted to improve the education system in America. He was a leading voice in the movement to improve schools through professional learning teams, where teachers come together to analyze and improve their classroom practices.

Despite being born blind, this did not stop Jeremy Bruner from succeeding, as he was able to obtain a PhD in psychology and taught at Harvard, Oxford and New York universities. Bruner always paid attention to the American education system and looked for ways to improve it. He introduced the concepts of discovery learning and spiral curriculum. Discovery learning is described as a way for students to independently study a given curriculum and build on their own experiences. Spiral learning was Bruner's idea that similar topics could be taught at any age, but according to the stage of thinking.[4]

David Kolb was inspired by Kurt Lewin, John Dewey, and Jean Piaget to create the experiential learning model. Kolb believed that effective learners should have concrete experience skills (CE), reflective observation skills (RO), abstract conceptualization (AC), and active experimentation (AE) skills. Specific experience is involved and actively participates in new experiences. Reflective observation is asking questions and discussing experience. Abstract conceptualization is when the learner thinks and begins to make inferences. Active experimentation is re-applying one's findings to a task to make decisions and solve problems.[2]

American economist and mathematician Kenneth Arrow emphasizes the importance of learning as a means of increasing labor productivity. In the article he writes: "But one empirical generalization is so clear that all schools of thought must accept it, even if they interpret it differently: learning is a product of experience. Learning is possible only during the attempt to solve the problem, and therefore only during the activity» - Kenneth J. Arrow (The Economic Implications of Learning by Doing).[5]

Project-based learning (LAT) is a student-centered pedagogy that involves a dynamic classroom approach in which students gain deeper knowledge through active exploration of real-world problems and issues. [2] Students learn a subject by working long hours to investigate and answer a complex question, problem, or issue.[3] It is an active learning and inquiry-based learning style. LAT differs from paper-based, rote, or teacher-led instruction that presents concrete facts or provides a smooth path to knowledge by posing questions, problems, or scenarios.[4]

HISTORY

John Dewey is one of the early proponents of project-based learning, or at least its principles are recognized through the idea of "learning by doing".[4] In "My Pedagogical Beliefs" (1897), Dewey listed his beliefs, including that "the teacher is not in the school to impose certain ideas or to form certain habits in the child, but society a 'is there to choose the effects that affect the child as a member?' should influence the child and help him to answer them correctly".[6] Therefore, he promoted expressive or constructive activity as the center of correlation.[6] Educational research has developed this idea of teaching and learning into a methodology known as "project-based learning." Based on the theory of his mentor, Dewey, William Hurd Kilpatrick introduced the project method as a component of Dewey's problem-based method of teaching[7].

Some scholars (for example, James G. Greeno) have linked project-based learning with Jean Piaget's "situated learning" perspective [8] and constructivist theories. Piaget put forward the idea of learning that does not focus on memorization. According to his theory, project-based teaching is a method that encourages students to invent and see learning as a process with a future, instead of taking the basics of knowledge as truth.[9]

Further development of project-based learning as a pedagogy came from experiential and cognitive-based theories of learning proposed by later theorists such as Jan Comenius, Johann Heinrich Pestalozzi, and Maria Montessori.[7]

Sherlock, developed by Alan M. Lesgold and Sherrie P. Gott, is an intelligent tutoring system that helps Airmen understand cognitive tasks in the Air Force. Sherlock's fast and efficient approach provides a training tool with support and feedback.[6] Sherlock will help if the student loses what he did. This support includes advice when the student is unsure of how to proceed to overcome knowledge gaps, and critical feedback and feedback to help the student continue to work effectively. Sherlock monitors the student's work using two models:

Competency Model: The extent to which each objective has been achieved. Any deviation of the student's performance from the predictions can be taken into account when updating his competency model.

Performance Model: How well the learner is expected to perform at each point in the abstracted problem space. It affects how Sherlock helps at certain points of the problem

A performance model provides guidance based on expected student performance. Hints come in the following form: Action, Result, Conclusion, and Option

Level 1: I am asking for advice for the first time. Advice on recapitulation (asking for help from adults).

Level 2: Good job rating

Level 3: Good grade

Level 4: Poor grade

Additional requests will lead to higher levels of advice until the issue is resolved. If there are no other Summary hints, Option hints are provided.[7]

"A project is a plan developed for a structure, building, creating something, etc. A set of documents reflecting the content of this plan (description, drawings, schemes, etc.). What? Conceived, designed to be implemented."

Similar in many ways, educational, research and project activities contain structural elements of each other. Thus, these types of activities complement each other (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Methodological component in project and educational research activity

EXAMPLES OF PROJECT WORK

A balloon car is one of the simplest physics projects that can be made using readily available items at home. Basic items needed to make a balloon machine include one plastic bottle, two straws, four bottle caps, one balloon, and glue. First of all, put the bottle horizontally on the table and make a hole on the curved surface of the bottle and two pairs of holes near the base. Cut

one straw in half, insert both pieces of straw into the pair of holes. Attach four bottle caps to the ends of the straws using glue. Make a hole in the top of the plastic bottle and fix the straw in the hole so that part of the straw lies on top and the rest inside the bottle. Attach the inflated balloon to the end of the straw at the top of the bottle. When the air from the balloon creates air pressure on the surface, the structure moves forward. Air pressure, state of matter, rotational motion, linear motion, transfer of motion from one form to another and various other physical parameters can be easily studied from this project.

Fountain – To create a fountain as a physics project, you will need plastic containers, wooden blocks, vinyl pipes, a water pump, electricity, a drill, rocks, miniature plants, a cutter and glue. Create your own fountain base using wooden blocks. Make a hole in the bottom of one of the plastic containers and another hole in the side of the other plastic container. Thread the vinyl tubing through both holes. Tape the tube around the joints and holes. Place the bowls on the wooden structure of the fountain in such a way that one of the bowls is taller than the other bowl. Make a hole in the front of the container above the main container. At the end of the pipe, attach a small water pump and connect it to the power source. Decorate the structure with stones, paints, miniature plants and more. Pour water into the bowls and watch the water flow like a fountain in a miniature pond. This project will help users to understand the flow of fluids, water pump operation, potential energy and kinetic energy.

CONCLUSION

In the process of project-based education, a certain learning problem is set under the guidance of the teacher, and students are given the task of solving it. In this way, the social activity of the students increases, they engage in mutual communication, and their scientific knowledge, skills and competences in searching for a solution to the problem increase, as well as mathematical literacy and competencies of using scientific and technical achievements are formed.

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